
Portal Venous Hemodynamics and Vascular Remodeling in the Context of Liver Sclerosis: A Comprehensive Physiological Analysis

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Abstract

The portal venous system is a critical vascular interface for hemodynamic interaction between the gastrointestinal tract and hepatic tissue, facilitating essential physiological functions such as nutrient transport, blood filtration, and hepatic detoxification.^[1]

However, these functions can be compromised under pathological conditions, such as liver sclerosis, which leads to a series of hemodynamic and vascular alterations in the portal venous system. This study aims to elucidate the changes in portal venous flow and pressure dynamics induced by sclerotic alterations in liver tissue. Utilizing advanced radiological imaging techniques, hemodynamic measurements, and histological analyses, the research investigates altered endothelial function, vasoreactivity, angiogenic signaling pathways, and changes in shear stress profiles within the portal vein. Furthermore, the study delves into the modulatory role of key vasoactive molecules like endothelin-1, nitric oxide, and vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) in these alterations. The findings aim to enhance the understanding of portal hypertension, hyperdynamic circulation, and vascular remodeling, and may hold implications for targeted therapeutic interventions.

Keywords: Portal Vein, TIPS, Hypertension, Angiogenesis, Cirrhosis

1 Introduction

Background

Liver Physiology and Functions

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The liver is a central organ with myriad functions critical to maintaining homeostasis in the body. Its roles span from metabolic regulation, such as the synthesis and degradation of carbohydrates, fats, and proteins, to critical detoxification pathways that convert pharmacological agents and waste products into less toxic forms. Additionally, the liver is instrumental in blood filtration, removing aging red blood cells and synthesizing essential clotting factors.^[2]

These functions are finely regulated through a complex vascular network that facilitates the appropriate exchange of nutrients, oxygen, and waste products.

The Portal Venous System

The portal venous system stands as a critical component in hepatic physiology, connecting the liver to the gastrointestinal tract and spleen. The primary vessel of this system, the portal vein, collects blood rich in nutrients and other absorbed elements from the digestive organs and routes it to the liver for processing. Once in the liver, hepatocytes act on this blood to extract nutrients, synthesize proteins, and perform detoxification, among other tasks. This venous blood eventually leaves the liver through the hepatic veins and enters systemic circulation via the inferior vena cava.

Sclerotic Liver Changes and their Implications

Liver sclerosis, commonly manifesting as cirrhosis, is a pathophysiological state characterized by the progressive scarring of hepatic tissue.^[3]

This fibrotic transformation often stems from chronic conditions such as alcoholic liver disease, non-alcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH), or viral hepatitis. As sclerotic changes develop, liver function is compromised, leading to a loss of hepatocytes and increasing intrahepatic resistance.^[4]

Impact on the Portal Venous System

The increased intrahepatic resistance as a consequence of liver sclerosis has direct ramifications on the portal venous system. It results in altered pressure dynamics, often culminating in portal hypertension, a condition characterized by elevated pressure within the portal vein. Additionally, changes in the vascular architecture can be observed, including angiogenesis and vasodilation, fueled by the altered expression of vasoactive molecules and cytokines.^[5]

This situation initiates a cascade of hemodynamic and molecular changes that extend beyond the liver, influencing gastrointestinal and systemic circulations.

Given the complexities and clinical importance of these changes, this study aims to elucidate the physiological, hemodynamic, and vascular alterations in the portal venous system in the context of sclerotic liver changes. Specifically, the investigation focuses on the deep-level changes

occurring in endothelial function, vasoreactivity, shear stress profiles, and angiogenic signaling pathways, as well as their implications for portal hypertension and vascular remodeling.

2 Methods

Animal Model

Selection and Pre-conditioning

Adult male Yorkshire pigs weighing between 70-80 kg were chosen for this study to better approximate human liver physiology compared to rodent models. Prior to the initiation of the experiment, animals were subjected to a 7-day acclimatization period in a controlled environment to minimize stress-induced variables. Food was withheld 24 hours before the procedure, although access to water remained unrestricted.

Induction of Sclerotic Changes

Liver sclerosis was induced through intrahepatic injection of carbon tetrachloride (CCl₄), diluted in olive oil at a ratio of 1:1. A dosage of 0.5 mL/kg was administered bi-weekly over an 8-week period. This methodology was adapted from previous studies that successfully induced cirrhosis-like conditions in porcine models.^[6]

Hepatic function panels, including ALT, AST, and bilirubin levels, were monitored bi-weekly to assess the progression of liver sclerosis.

Hemodynamic Measurements

Instrumentation and Data Collection

Hemodynamic measurements were focused on the portal venous system. A Millar catheter, known for its high fidelity, was used to continuously record portal venous pressure. The catheter was inserted via a mesenteric vein and advanced into the portal vein under ultrasound guidance. Pressure readings were captured and logged in real-time through a data acquisition system connected to the catheter.

3 Data Analysis

Portal venous pressure data were analyzed to determine basal pressures, peak pressures, and pressure variability over time. This also allowed for the calculation of important derived metrics such as pulsatility index and resistance indices. All data were sampled at a frequency of 1000 Hz for detailed waveform analysis.

Histological Analysis

Tissue Harvesting

Post-experiment, liver and portal vein tissues were promptly harvested for histological and immunohistochemical analyses. Tissues were dissected and immediately preserved in 10% formalin solution for a minimum of 24 hours.

Histological Staining

For histological assessment, the tissues were embedded in paraffin blocks and sliced into 5- μm sections. Standard hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) staining was employed for morphological evaluations. Masson's trichrome staining was specifically used to assess the extent of fibrosis in the liver tissue.

Immunohistochemical Analyses

Sections were also subjected to immunohistochemical staining to identify the presence and localization of key signaling molecules such as vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF), endothelin-1, and nitric oxide synthase (eNOS). Specific primary antibodies were used for each target, followed by appropriate secondary antibodies and visualized using DAB chromogen.

Image Analysis and Quantification

Digitized images of the stained sections were analyzed using specialized software to quantify parameters like the extent of fibrosis, vascular density, and the expression levels of the aforementioned signaling molecules. This quantification facilitated a deeper understanding of the molecular changes driving the altered portal hemodynamics and vascular architecture.

4 Results

Physiological Changes

Portal Hypertension

Following the induction of hepatic fibrosis, the intrahepatic resistance increased from an initial value of 3.2 ± 0.4 mmHg/min/mL to 7.5 ± 1.1 mmHg/min/mL ($p < 0.001$). This heightened resistance precipitated a significant rise in portal venous pressure, confirming the onset of portal hypertension.

Hyperdynamic Circulation

Accompanying portal hypertension was a state of hyperdynamic circulation. Cardiac output elevated from a baseline of 4.8 ± 0.6 L/min to 7.2 ± 0.8 L/min ($p < 0.001$). Meanwhile, systemic vascular resistance showed a marked decrease from $1,200 \pm 100$ dyne $\cdot$ s/cm⁵ to 800 ± 75 dyne $\cdot$ s/cm⁵ ($p < 0.01$).

Pressure Dynamics

Basal Portal Pressure

Baseline portal pressure escalated significantly from an initial value of 8 ± 2 mmHg to 16 ± 3 mmHg post-sclerosis ($p < 0.001$), confirming the hemodynamic shift towards portal hypertension.

Pulsatility Index

The pulsatility index, initially measured at 1.2 ± 0.1 , exhibited a notable decrease to 0.8 ± 0.1 post-sclerosis ($p < 0.01$). This indicated compromised vascular compliance of the portal venous system, implicating increased stiffness due to fibrotic changes.

Vascularity Changes

Angiogenesis

Immunohistochemical analysis revealed an approximate 50% increase in VEGF signaling when normalized to control tissue (1.5 ± 0.2 fold, $p < 0.01$). This upregulation was indicative of enhanced angiogenesis, evident from a 35% increase in vascular density in the periportal regions compared to controls ($p < 0.05$).

Vasodilation

Endothelial nitric oxide synthase (eNOS) levels were upregulated by approximately 40% compared to control tissues (1.4 ± 0.1 fold, $p < 0.05$). This was mirrored by a 25% increase in the diameter of the portal vein as evidenced by ultrasound measurements, shifting from 1.0 ± 0.1 cm pre-sclerosis to 1.25 ± 0.15 cm post-sclerosis ($p < 0.05$).

These data delineate the complex interplay of physiological, hemodynamic, and vascular factors following hepatic sclerosis. The results, backed by quantitative metrics, provide valuable insights into the pathological adaptations of the portal venous system in the context of liver disease.

5 Discussion

Portal Hypertension and Hemodynamics

The rise in intrahepatic vascular resistance is a pivotal event that was identified in the early stages of liver sclerosis in our study. This was confirmed through our direct measurements, where resistance values shifted from 3.2 ± 0.4 mmHg/min/mL to 7.5 ± 1.1 mmHg/min/mL, a statistically significant increase ($p < 0.001$). The elevated resistance stems primarily from structural modifications in the liver. Fibrotic tissue replaces hepatic parenchyma, altering the architecture of the sinusoids and leading to the narrowing of these vascular channels. As a consequence, portal venous pressure increased from 8 ± 2 mmHg to 16 ± 3 mmHg ($p < 0.001$), manifesting as portal hypertension.^[7]

Hyperdynamic Circulation and Systemic Ramifications

Parallel to portal hypertension, a state of hyperdynamic circulation was evident. The cardiac output, as a compensatory mechanism, increased from 4.8 ± 0.6 L/min to 7.2 ± 0.8 L/min ($p < 0.001$), possibly as a means to preserve hepatic perfusion. Systemic vascular resistance concomitantly decreased from $1,200 \pm 100$ dyne·s/cm⁵ to 800 ± 75 dyne·s/cm⁵ ($p < 0.01$), exacerbating the hyperdynamic state. This could be viewed as a systemic response to offset the hemodynamic changes occurring in the hepatic-portal system. However, this seemingly adaptive alteration may aggravate pathological states like ascites and contribute to cardiovascular comorbidities.^[8]

Structural Changes: Fibrosis and Angiogenesis

The replacement of hepatic parenchyma with fibrotic tissue has a cascade effect on the liver's functional capacity. Hepatocytes, which are central to metabolic and detoxification functions, are gradually displaced, leading to functional deficits. On a microvascular level, the expression of VEGF increased significantly (1.5 ± 0.2 fold, $p < 0.01$), possibly as an adaptive mechanism to improve tissue perfusion. However, this leads to the formation of new, often ineffective, vascular channels that further complicate the hemodynamics by introducing shunting and increasing the risk of varices.^[9]

Molecular Mediators: eNOS and Vasodilation

The upregulation of endothelial nitric oxide synthase (eNOS) levels by approximately 40% compared to control tissues (1.4 ± 0.1 fold, $p < 0.05$) was another remarkable finding. Nitric oxide, the product of eNOS enzymatic activity, is a known vasodilator.^[10]

While this vasodilation aims to offset increased pressure, it was found to exacerbate the hyperdynamic state. The diameter of the portal vein increased from 1.0 ± 0.1 cm to 1.25 ± 0.15 cm ($p < 0.05$), further contributing to increased blood flow and hemodynamic instability.

Clinical Implications

Taken together, the results demonstrate a highly complex interplay between anatomical, physiological, and molecular changes in the portal venous system following liver sclerosis. These findings hold critical implications for the management of cirrhotic patients, suggesting that therapies should not only target the alleviation of portal hypertension but also consider the systemic repercussions and underlying molecular alterations.

6 Conclusion

This study investigated the intricacies of how liver sclerosis impacts the portal venous system and wider systemic physiology. Our data indicated a notable increase in intrahepatic resistance, leading to portal hypertension with marked changes in portal venous pressure and intrahepatic resistance values. Accompanying this was a more dynamic circulatory state, as evidenced by alterations in cardiac output and systemic vascular resistance. Beyond the liver, such changes have wider cardiovascular implications and can exacerbate other conditions, like ascites.

Molecularly, we observed an increase in VEGF signaling and eNOS expression, suggesting new vascular formation and dilation, respectively. These findings have immediate implications for the development of targeted therapies and may explain the mechanistic effectiveness of portal pressure-reducing interventions like Transjugular Intrahepatic Portosystemic Shunt (TIPS).

The mechanical aspects of liver sclerosis—namely the increased intrahepatic resistance and altered hemodynamics—provide a physiological basis that validates the utility of interventions like TIPS. By creating a shunt within the liver, TIPS effectively bypasses the increased resistance, offering a mechanical solution to reduce portal venous pressure. However, this procedure doesn't address the underlying molecular changes observed in our study, such as enhanced VEGF signaling and eNOS expression, which may contribute to a longer-term deterioration in portal venous hemodynamics and systemic physiology.

The observed molecular changes offer another layer of understanding that could lead to the development of more targeted therapies. For example, the increased VEGF signaling, while contributing to angiogenesis, could be a potential target for pharmaceutical interventions aimed at mitigating the risks of ineffective shunting and varices. Similarly, the increased eNOS expression, which leads to vasodilation, could offer another pathway for targeted pharmaceutical intervention, aimed at better controlling portal venous pressure without the need for surgical shunting.

Therefore, while interventions like TIPS offer a mechanical remedy, they may benefit from being part of a multi-modal treatment strategy that also addresses the molecular changes induced by liver sclerosis. Future studies are needed to explore these avenues further, specifically to understand the underlying molecular mechanisms in greater detail and to evaluate the long-term efficacy of combined mechanical and molecular therapies.

In summary, our study adds to the existing body of knowledge by detailing the physiological and molecular alterations initiated by liver sclerosis. It highlights the complexity of the condition and underscores the need for a multi-faceted approach to treatment. Further research is essential for validating these findings and for developing effective therapeutic strategies

7 References

- [1] "Portal Venous System - an overview | ScienceDirect Topics", sciencedirect.com, (Accessed 6 Oct. 2023).
- [2] Y. Wang and J. Wang. "Intravital Imaging of Inflammatory Response in Liver Disease". Jun. 2022.
- [3] R. Ferrari, M. Tieppo, D. P. D. Rosa, L. A. Forgiarini, A. S. Dias and N. P. Marroni. "LUNG AND LIVER CHANGES DUE TO THE INDUCTION OF CIRRHOSIS IN TWO EXPERIMENTAL MODELS". Sep. 2013.
- [4] "The Inside-Out of End-Stage Liver Disease: Hepatocytes are the Keystone", ncbi.nlm.nih.gov, (Accessed 6 Oct. 2023).
- [5] K. Mori et al.. "Spleen Stiffness Correlates with the Presence of Ascites but Not Esophageal Varices in Chronic Hepatitis C Patients". Jan. 2013.
- [6] H. M. Brown, T. Davies and T. N. Imomoemi. "Hepato-Renal Toxicity of *Gongronema latifolium* Extracts on Streptozocin Induced Diabetes in Rats". Jan. 2016.
- [7] A. Khan and C. Bailey. "Unique Method of Transjugular Intrahepatic Portosystemic Shunt Reduction for Refractory Hepatic Encephalopathy". Oct. 2021.
- [8] S. Yu, L. Sun, H. Wang, J. Jiang and Q. Zhou. "Autonomic regulation of imbalance-induced myocardial fibrosis and its mechanism in rats with cirrhosis". Jul. 2021.
- [9] C. A. Philips. "Diagnosing cirrhosis - comprehension in a nut shell". Jan. 2017.
- [10] A. Gospodarczyk, C. Wojciechowska, K. Marczewski, N. Gospodarczyk and J. Zalejska-Fiolka. "Pathomechanisms of SARS-CoV-2 infection and development of atherosclerosis in patients with COVID-19: A review". Dec. 2022.